

Orthopteroids, general and fossils

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FOSSILS. All orthopteroids from the Carboniferous onwards share the same veinal characters, fusion, and struts.

Orthoptera Stem Group

Oedischiidae: *Oedischia williamsoni* Brogniart, Upper Carboniferous, France

Notable Plesiomorphy: veinal corrugations is regular (not as in modern Neoptera!)

Orthopteroid ground plan veinal characters (differences from "Treatise"):

1. M & CuA fusion present
2. Stem of Cu absent (!) (basal plesiomorphy)
3. Cu branches, braced with CuA by a strut
4. ScA richly branched
5. Stem of M present (basal apomorphy of Orthopteroid lineage)

Triassic Orthopteroids

FW Aeroplanidae: *Aeroplana mirabilis* Till., 1918 M. Triassic Ipswich

FW Titanoptera: *Clatrotitan scullyi* Tilyard, 1925 Triassic

Paleozoic Orthoneoptera share veinal patterns

Permian, Checarda, Russia

Permian, Checarda, Russia

Caloneurodea, Checarda, Pin $\frac{1700}{1424}$
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Hind wings of orthoneoptera and blattoneoptera are very different

Orthoneoptera:

- A full anojugal lobe (plesiomorphic) is shared only with the Pleconeoptera.
- ScP long (plesiomorphy)
- ScA long (plesiomorphy)
- Stem of M present (apomorphy, as only in Pleco-M and MP (at length) fused with CuA (apomorphy)
- Stem of Cu absent (plesiomorphy)
- CuP richly branched (plesiomorphy)
- Strut CuA-CuP present (apomorphy)
- This veinal system has several unique plesiomorphic and apomorphic characters.

Blattoneoptera (as also Hemineoptera and Endoneoptera have many similar apo.- and plesio-characters):

- Partial anojugal lobe (apomorphy)
- ScA short, low ridge (apomorphy)
- ScP short (apomorphy)
- Stem of M absent (plesio)
- MA fused at length with R and RP (apo.)
- Short stem of Cu present, CuP often reduced (apo.)
- Strut MP-CuA (arculus) often present (apo.)

See also: Haas and Kukalová-Peck 2001, Dermaptera: structure....

Wing characters indicate the above tree of Neopteran lineages.

NEOPTERAN HIND WING VEINAL PATTERNS CHARACTERISTIC FOR LINEAGES

Veinal pattern of Orthoneoptera is the most different. Pleconeoptera share with the rest of Neoptera a similar support for anterior wing margin and presence of the cubital stem, while Blattoneoptera & Hemineoptera & Endoneoptera share derived anojugal lobe starting at the anal fold and a long R & MA fusion supporting long wing axis (see fig. 22).

Orthoneoptera: a very unusual veinal Pattern

Orthoptera have a very unusual combination of characters: plesiomorphic full anal lobes (with richly branched AA 1+2) and many highly derived fusions between veinal sectors at the wing base (ScP & R; MA & MP; M & CuA; MP & CuA). These key characters probably denote orthopteroids as the sister group of the rest of Pterygota.

Phasmatodea
Pallophidae
Palophus sp.